

Research Paper

Regarding the generation of time resolved industrial waste heat profiles

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ABSTRACT

The timely transient energy supply or insufficient temperature levels of industrial waste heat (IWH) hinders the full exploitation of its energy and CO₂ emission reduction potentials. This outlines the necessity for investigating IWH in a time resolved manner, which, however, is still widely disregarded, especially in generalized industrial energy system analyses and research. Within this study, we present our developed first-of-its-kind approach, which addresses this topic from a holistic system perspective and enables the generation of time resolved IWH profiles for all industrial subsectors. The backbone of our approach is the distinction of energy-intensive subsectors (e.g. Non-Metallic Minerals) and non-energy-intensive subsectors (e.g. Food & Beverage Production), as both vary in regard to their underlying process designs, production routines and data accessibility. Concerning the first group we found that time resolved IWH profiles can be generated by combining process specific data in a bottom-up manner with temperature gradients of the whole production route throughout the paradigm of discrete event simulation. We investigated further that IWH profiles of non-energy-intensive subsectors are depicted by examining existing subsector resolved waste heat fractions and combining this information with plant-specific load profiles in a top-down manner. We practically prove our findings for both groups within (1) a case study of generating IWH profiles of a real-life cement production mill as part of energy-intensive subsectors and (2) outline the analysis of waste heat fractions for the non-energy-intensive subsector of food production exemplarily. Both cases reflect the above findings successfully and with satisfactory results, which can therefore be regarded as basis for future research work concerning time resolved IWH.

1. Introduction

The exploitation of industrial waste heat (IWH) is regarded as a go-to solution for reducing the energy consumption and CO₂ emissions of industrial plants [1]. From a systemic point of view, IWH is utilized internally for site-specific heating and/or externally within district heating grids for further usage off-site (e.g., in residential buildings). The International Energy Agency (IEA) foresees the exploitation of the maximum economic potential of IWH to be achieved by 2030 [2]. The current deployment status is still far off this maximum. For example, energy system analyses of the European industrial sector estimate current unused technical potentials to still amount to up to 817 TWh/a [3]. From a technical point of view, besides temperature issues, a major limiting factor concerning the utilization of these untapped potentials is caused by the fluctuating, timely instability of generated waste heat [4]. This hinders a constant supply of thermal energy for consumers and therefore requires additional efforts to be considered by e.g., energy

system development, deployment of demand side management (DSM) and storage measures.

A solution for bridging the challenges of unstable IWH on a holistic energy system level lies in the generation of time resolved IWH profiles. As a result, future analyses of industrial energy systems can easily assess the potential of IWH for internal or external utilization for different industries, production sizes and time frames. Following this context, our goal within this study is to present an approach, which covers the generation of IWH profiles for manufacturing sites and for the entirety of the industrial sector.

1.1. State of research

Within the context of our research aim of time resolved IWH analysis and generation, we conducted an extensive literature review of current studies also dedicated in adjacent research fields of industrial energy systems. In general, we found that existing studies mainly cover two

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areas:

1. Studies, which quantify waste heat spatially as a source for e.g., external use in district heating grids on a high aggregated level. This research mainly applies low aggregation time frames like months or years for their respective assessments.
2. Studies on individual process and technology level, which examine novel technological advancements into e.g., existing industrial designs for more efficient site own use. This research generally applies detailed data on a high timely resolution in e.g., seconds or minutes to assure the technology's system integration.

To provide a better overview of both fields, we allocated these categories to industrial aggregation levels in Fig. 1. Followingly, we provide a more detailed description of both categories and outline the resulting research gap, which we address in this study.

For the first category, as an example, McKenna et al. [5] present an energetic and exergetic analysis-based model for assessing waste heat loads and their technical recovery potentials for the entire industrial sector in the UK. Therefore, the authors calculate the respective heat load of various sites of several industrial subsectors based on emission trading system (ETS) reports. The IWH recovery potentials are then assessed via heat recovery fractions from measured manufacturing plants from other sources. These analyses bear important information on the cross-sectoral industry-to-heating-grid IWH potentials, however, do not consider detailed time resolved behaviour as they solely incorporate yearly data. Persson et al. [3] and Brueckner et al. [6] conduct similar analyses for Europe and Germany respectively for different years.

The second category of research studies involves heat recovery technologies and site-specific recovery opportunities on individual process and technology level. Here, the focus lies on the industrial implementation of novel technologies and assessing their economic and technical feasibility for recovering IWH for e.g., internal usage. To thoroughly proof a successful system integration of the respective technology, the time resolved generation of IWH on-site is significant. Within this context, Lecompte et al. [7], for instance, conduct a case study for incorporating an organic Rankine cycle (ORC) for recovering IWH within an electric arc furnace (EAF) mill. Because the EAF is operated batch-wise, IWH is only generated time varyingly. The authors state the challenges in implementing IWH recovery technologies for timely unstable production behaviour and point out the necessity of examining the time resolved generation of IWH in terms of IWH profiles.

In another example, Dock et al. [8] present a model for investigating energy and CO₂ emission reduction in an EAF mill. Here, the time resolved energy consumption in terms of load profiles (LPs) forms the basis of the study. Dock et al. further generate IWH profiles to investigate the time resolved IWH generation, internal recovery and process integration on-site to reach their desired aim.

In general, the consensus within state-of-the-art studies seizes the challenges caused by the characterizing influence of the time-dependent production and process behaviour on IWH generation in industry [4]. The usage of waste heat potentials – internally as well as externally – must be subordinated to the production design. Thus, the time resolved supply from IWH does in general not resemble the time resolved heat demand – internally and externally. This is especially true when investigating batch processes that are not operated continuously and therefore strongly influence the fluctuation of IWH supply. Literature studies above state that it is necessary to thoroughly examine the fluctuation of IWH to fully exploit its energy consumption and CO₂ emission reduction potential.

As a result from our literature research, we conclude that subsector specific, high aggregated analyses and concrete technological studies on low aggregation levels are already well developed. However, we investigated that – to our knowledge – no studies connected both groups and transferred their generated knowledge onto plant level in a time resolved context. Within this study, we, therefore, investigate time resolved IWH generation and utilization on plant level for the entire industrial sector by the generation of IWH profiles. This will bridge the gap between both already addressed categories and brings potentials to more detailed holistic energy system analyses e.g., developing decarbonization scenarios, or for embedding individual technological advancements into more comprehensive energy systems (e.g., heating grids). This interconnection is shown in Fig. 1 and forms the research gap, we address with our work.

1.2. Research hypotheses and structure of this paper

Information on cross-sectoral spatial IWH utilization and process specific waste heat data is already put in place by various studies, as shown above. We found that the time resolved behaviour of IWH generation and utilization on plant level is not examined thoroughly yet. However, to fully exploit the whole potential industry internal and external IWH utilization might bear, this issue is a mandatory research area to be handled. As the generation of IWH profiles shall be examined

Fig. 1. Comparison of current research areas regarding IWH utilization in industry and aim of this study: Spatial models, which investigate external use within district heating grids on a high aggregated level and low time resolution or technology-based analyses for internal, on-site use with high level of detail in time resolution. Research gap for time resolved IWH generation and utilization on plant level is still unaddressed.

for the entire industrial sector, the following situated hypotheses are to be validated within this study:

- H1: System boundaries are crucial when investigating IWH utilization. The adaption of system boundaries will alter the corresponding IWH profiles in terms of both time and temperature-resolved patterns.
- H2: The generation of IWH profiles demands data regarding operating temperatures and time resolved properties of all process steps within the to-be-investigated single processes or overall production routes.
- H3: IWH is subject to specific time resolved fluctuations. Therefore, industrial energy systems require a timely assessment and optimization to thoroughly exploit the full IWH recovery potential.

We will prove these hypotheses throughout this study. To initiate our investigations, a precise definition of IWH (section 2.1) and applicable industrial system boundaries (section 2.2) is crucial within our developed study. After classifying the industrial sector as energy-intensive and non-energy-intensive, the respective IWH assessment methodologies are described in sections 2.3 and 2.4. We furthermore conduct a case study generating synthetic IWH profiles and validating the selected results in section 3. Finally, section 4 concludes this study by reflecting on the hypotheses stated above.

2. Methodology

To kick-off our methodology, we split the industrial sector into energy-intensive and non-energy-intensive subsectors, defined by the IEA [9]. Within our prior study [10] we found that the first group exhibits higher energy consumption but relies on a smaller number of production processes, while non-energy-intensive subsectors produce more complex products via a large number of varying production principles. For both groups, their respective shares of primary energy consumption in Austria are outlined in Fig. 2 exemplarily. We show that, although energy-intensive subsectors exhibit higher shares of energy consumption, non-energy-intensive subsectors exceed regarding their number [11]. Due to their different characteristics and underlying heterogeneity concerning products, processes and production routines, both groups are to be approached via different methodologies.

Within our prior studies [10], we developed a methodology for generating load profiles (LPs) for energy-intensive and non-energy intensive subsectors. Regarding the first, the methodology for generating IWH profiles is tightly interlinked with the existing bottom-up approach of the sequencing and process execution logic of discrete event simulation for generating synthetic LPs. We extended the classification of all involved processes within these subsectors by waste heat data such as intake, operating and outlet temperature, thermal energy flow rate, the waste heat energy carrier, etc. We retrieved these data from literature studies, which examine IWH on process level and technical recovery potentials on the low aggregated level outlined in Fig. 1. These process specific parameters present in combination the technical

Fig. 2. Share of primary energy consumption of non-energy-intensive and energy-intensive industrial subsectors in Austria; Developed methodologies for both groups.

recovery potentials of the process. The utilization of this IWH is realized within our methodology via sensible or latent heat transfer within dedicated HEXs. The time resolved operation of the processes is then interlinked with waste heat generation, internal waste heat recovery/consumption, and external waste heat utilization. In combination with the also generated LPs, IWH profiles are generated.

The methodology for non-energy-intensive subsectors does not incorporate process specific information hence the subsectors' complexity of processes and production routines. Here, we conducted extensive literature research on subsector-specific data regarding output IWH recovery fractions, determined based on measurements and plant-specific emissions on high-aggregated level as also outlined in Fig. 1. The combination of these recovery fractions with existing LPs allows for the calculation of synthetic IWH profiles.

2.1. Definition and classification of generated IWH

For the development of a comprehensive methodology, which enables the generation of synthetic time resolved IWH profiles for different systemic boundaries and industrial subsectors, a concise definition of IWH is a crucial factor. Within our study, we define IWH as energy that is rejected by industrial processing units, which operate at temperatures above ambient temperature [12]. The excess energy is carried by a waste heat energy carrier, whose thermal energy flow rate \dot{Q}_{IWH} [W] is driven by either sensible or latent heat transfer. Sensible heat transfer thermodynamically applies, when a system remains in one phase and the heat from or to the system is depicted via a temperature difference as formula (1) explains:

$$\dot{Q}_{IWH} = \dot{m}_{Carrier} \times c_{p,Carrier} \times \Delta T \quad \text{with } \Delta T = T_{outlet} - T_{ambient} \quad (1)$$

with $\dot{m}_{Carrier}$ [kg/s] as the mass flow of the waste heat energy carrier, $c_{p,Carrier}$ [J/(kg K)] specific heat capacity of the waste heat energy carrier and ΔT the temperature difference [K] between process outlet temperature T_{outlet} (hot-end at heat transfer) and reference / minimum use temperature T_{min} or $T_{ambient}$ (cold-end at heat transfer), which we refer to the ambient temperature in this study [13]. Per the principle of energy conservation, the process outlet temperature has to be equal to or lower than the operating temperature of the process itself.

Latent heat transfer applies for systems within phase transition (e.g., steam generation). The heat absorbed or emitted is directly involved in this transitional process, which is driven under constant temperature. The corresponding waste heat is calculated through formula (2):

$$\dot{Q}_{IWH} = \dot{m}_{Carrier} \times h_{Carrier} \quad (2)$$

with $\dot{m}_{Carrier}$ [kg/s] as the mass flow and $h_{Carrier}$ [J/kg] as specific latent heat of the of the waste heat energy carrier.

Fig. 3 shows these definitions together with a respective \dot{Q}/T diagram of the rejected energy flow of process P1 as sensible or latent heat transportation.

Depending on the energy flow rate and technical feasibility, a fraction of this rejected energy can be recovered for useful purposes either internally within the industrial plant itself and/or externally as input for district heating grids [14]. The method for generating the utilization of these IWH potentials is also conducted via sensible or latent heat transfer.

This recovery process, in general, is deployed by incorporating a closed or open heat exchanging network with a respective carrier medium e.g., thermal oil, hot water, etc. Different technologies can be applied for this recovery. Brueckner et al. [6] divide these technologies in direct and indirect categories according to their planned usage. Direct systems recover IWH and utilize it as the same form of energy, while indirect technologies convert the heat into other energy forms. Thus, heat pumps, heat exchangers, boilers, thermal heat storages and refrigeration cycles are direct heat recovery technologies, whilst thermoelectric generators, ORC, Kalina cycles, etc. transform the collected waste heat into electric or mechanical power [15]. Throughout both categories, input energy consumption, which would require a conservative energy supply, can be reduced. We outline novel technological developments in both groups: Within direct technologies, especially high temperature heat pumps are in focus in recent research endeavours as e.g., Jiang et al. [16] present the low global warming potentials of centrifugal heat pumps supplied with IWH for temperature ranges above 100 °C with new refrigerant components. In another example, Jouhara et al. [17] show the application of heat pipe heat exchangers in energy-intensive industries via a theoretical model and practical implementation. The authors outline the importance of novel recovery technologies in high-temperature industries like energy-intensive subsectors and present a scalable guideline for implementing heat pipes in other locations. For indirect recovery technologies, Miao et al. [18] examined recently the impact of unstable IWH generation on thermoelectric generators and concluded that certain patterns of IWH instability can also lead to improvement in thermoelectric power generation. Piri et al. [19] combine compressed-air energy storages with a multiple-step Kalina recovery cycle and outline the future potential of its system integration.

To thoroughly assess the accumulated IWH for both single processes and overall production routes in industry, we introduced an exergetic classification of the rejected and recovered energy. Table 1 shows the classification of exergetic levels of the IWH, separated into different

Fig. 3. Process P1 specific waste heat; Definitions of temperatures and energy flows as well as \dot{Q}/T diagrams for (a) sensible or (b) latent heat generation.

Table 1
Exergetic levels of IWH for different temperature ranges.

Exergetic Level	Temperature Range/Level
Low-grade IWH	$T_{\text{ambient}} - 50\text{ °C}$
Medium-grade IWH	$50\text{ °C} - 100\text{ °C}$
High-grade IWH	$100\text{ °C} - 400\text{ °C}$
Very High-grade IWH	$>400\text{ °C}$

temperature ranges. The recovery potential rises with increasing IWH grading [15].

The rejected energy is carried by waste heat energy carriers. These vary regarding their properties like composition, material, state, etc. We agreed upon classifying four waste heat energy carriers: “Flue Gas”, “Exhaust/Cooling Air”, “Waste/Cooling Water” and “Steam and Air with Condensable Water”, as shown in Table 2. We disregarded changes in the material composition and overall system pressure. We furthermore assumed that steam is saturated and utilized at 12 bars within industrial energy systems. Superheated steam is not included in our calculations. For “Flue Gas”, “Exhaust/Cooling Air” and “Waste/Cooling Water” we apply sensible heat transfer in line with formula (1). “Steam and Air with Condensable Water” refers to phase transitional processes like described above and applies latent heat transfer within our IWH calculations.

All waste heat analyses conducted in this study are regarded as theoretical technical potentials as defined by Panayiotou et al. [20]. As part of the technical potential, the theoretical technical potential is calculated by applying theoretical or generic process specific analyses. The deployed calculations deliver time resolved IWH potentials, which can be recovered by extracting the heat from the waste heat energy carrier and utilizing it again.

Within our study, we restrict our methodology to depict the potentials of time resolved IWH and its utilization via latent and sensible heat transfer within the direct technology of general heat exchangers (e.g., heat pipes). We do not depict other recovery technologies like thermal energy storage, ORC, etc. yet.

Furthermore, we conduct no optimization measures within time resolved IWH generation (e.g. pinch point analysis, loss limitation, ...) as our research goal is to generate synthetic IWH profiles for holistic energy system analyses. Via the application of synthetic IWH profiles, impacts of industrial plants on the overall energy system via e.g. district heating can be assessed more thoroughly and with an improved timely resolution.

2.2. System boundaries of industrial plants

Due to the diverse utilization of generated IWH within or outside industrial plants, we introduced system boundaries for adequate allocated calculations in our methodology. These system boundaries act as a holistic template and can be superimposed for every manufacturing plant for each industrial subsector.

Fig. 4 shows the defined system boundaries for an industrial plant in general. The system consists of units for energy conversion and

Table 2
Classification of waste heat energy carriers and their descriptions.

Waste Heat Energy Carrier	Description
Flue Gas	Carrier of sensible heat which originates from combustion processes
Exhaust/Cooling Air	Waste heat potentials from hot or warm products from production (e.g., product puffer), plant indoor exhaust air or machine cooling
Waste/Cooling Water	Water based waste heat potentials which leave production processes and originates from cleaning or cooling purposes
Steam and Air with Condensable Water	Steam as energy carrier or condensation of water within flue gas from/for evaporation or drying purposes

consumption. Furthermore, we introduced two systemic levels into this scheme. The plant level acts as the plant’s border. The public grid is located outside this boundary and all units outside this perimeter are not owned by the manufacturing plant [21]. The conservative energy supply route corresponds to the energy flow into and within the plant, which does not include IWH recovered flows. The energy distribution unit receives energy from outside the plant from the grid e.g., electricity or gas. This unit is responsible for supplying all other units within the plant-level border. However, the energy distribution unit can also receive energy from within the border, e.g., in case of on-site energy generation via PV or CHP plants or in case of recovered thermal energy. The latter can then be submitted to the public grid, e.g., within district heating networks. The manufacturing level lies within the plant border and contains all processes which are directly involved in value-creating production. Production auxiliary units like ventilation, lighting, etc. are located outside the manufacturing level. Within this border final energy, e.g., electricity or gas, is converted to useful energy, e.g., heat or mechanical drive. IWH can be generated within the plant at different units and recovered by deployed direct recovery technologies of heat exchangers as described in section 2.1. Within our definitions, IWH is generated within energy converting units like the on-site energy generation, final energy transformation or process own useful energy consumption. The energy recovery system applies heat exchangers to recover IWH internally (via the loop back into the manufacturing level) or utilize IWH externally within local district heating grids.

In general, the developed system boundaries can be allocated either to the manufacturing level, which results in IWH profiles of all production processes, or the plant level, which contains IWH profiles for waste heat leaving the facility, which meets our initial research aim.

2.3. Methodology for energy-intensive subsectors

As mentioned above, due to homogeneous production schemes of energy-intensive subsectors, we extended the already developed bottom-up approach for generating synthetic LPs to include IWH calculations.

We present a standardized process through which the time resolved IWH potentials of any user- or pre-defined production route can be allocated for recovery within or outside the facility. Its chronological order is shown in Fig. 5. At first, the potentials of generated IWH for the user- or pre-defined production processes are assessed via literature surveys. In the second step, the IWH recovery can be depicted via sensible or latent heat transfer. The excess, time resolved IWH, which is not recovered within the facility, is then calculated for external or additional internal utilization in terms of exploiting its technical potential. All results offer time resolved IWH profiles at the end of this depicted methodology. Analyses of economic feasibility are not included within the calculations but can be done in an additional post-processing step.

2.3.1. Assessment of technical IWH potentials

The backbone of IWH profile generation for energy-intensive subsectors is discrete event simulation. This simulation paradigm depicts the timely interaction of discrete products (e.g. tonnes of steel) with individual production processes [22]. The sequence of interactions is defined by designed production routes containing these processes. When an interaction with a process takes place, a corresponding process specific energy consumption profile is generated. As a result, a cumulative LP of the respective energy carrier is created. We developed this approach in our preceding study to generate synthetic LPs of energy-intensive industries [10].

This time resolved energy demand analysis acts as the basis for further IWH generation and consumption calculations, because these time resolved profiles are tightly interlinked with the production behaviour and energy input of each process [4]. This means, that a process cannot generate waste heat if it’s currently not in a producing state, e.g., turned off. As our aim is to generate time resolved IWH

Fig. 4. Overall industrial system boundary for allocation of IWH flows within and outside a fictitious industry plant.

Fig. 5. Process of assessing time resolved IWH for the selected production routes in our methodology.

profiles on higher aggregated plant level, any thermal inertia effects are already included in the averaged IWH potentials from individual processes or in the process state of ramp-down. In conclusion, the time resolved behaviour of energy demand and generating waste heat for each process has to follow the same pattern of process states e.g., off, ramp-up, producing, etc.

Within our methodology, we defined a process classifying system (see Table 3). All properties are pre-defined with process specific values from literature research and can be adapted freely by the user.

Regarding the collection of IWH properties of processes, we conducted an extensive literature review for standardised production routes, which we originally defined in our prior study [10]. This approach is practically outlined in our developed case study in section 3. In general, process and subsector specific studies present data on operating temperatures. For example, Feng et al. [23] investigate the conservative iron and steel production route via blast furnaces and outline the operating temperature of the sintering plant to be around 1300 °C. Besides this, we retrieved the data on technical IWH potentials (outlet temperatures, thermal energy flows, waste heat energy carriers) either through own calculations or literature survey again: Regarding the latter, we investigated recent (heat exchanger) direct recovery technologies for the respective production routes in literature. For example, Caputo et al. [24] present data for the technical IWH potential of radiant heat exchangers for rotary kilns in cement production routes. The

Table 3

Process classification in our methodology, divided into existing process properties for generating synthetic LPs and adapted IWH properties.

	Batch Operated Process	Continuous Operated Process
Standard Process Properties	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unit Size [t] • Turnover Time [min] • Operating Time [min] • Specific Energy Consumption [kWh/t] • Energy Consumption Time Series [kWh/t per min] • Material Stream Reference Stochastic Settings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Throughput/Capacity [t/h] • Specific Energy Consumption [kWh/t] • Material Stream Reference • Stochastic Settings
IWH Properties	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intake Temperature [°C] • Operating Temperature [°C] • Outlet Temperature of IWH [°C] • Thermal Energy Flow [kWh/t] or Mass Flow [kg/s] and Specific Thermal Capacity [kJ/(kg K)] of Waste Heat Energy Carrier • Waste Heat Energy Carrier 	

authors conclude that a maximum of 34.7 % of the total fuel input can be technically recovered from housed-in heat exchangers. This data is applicable to thermal energy flow of exhaust air within our methodology. For processes which bear technical IWH recovery potentials but

lack underlying data in literature, we applied thermodynamic calculations on heat transfer from fuel input for retrieving their theoretic potentials. In a next step, we estimated efficiency factors for depicting their technical potential.

Fig. 6 explains the overall methodology for IWH-generating processes for energy-intensive industry sectors and the generation of simplified, time resolved profiles. Here, a production route with two processes (P1, P2) – aligned sequentially – is supplied with specific energy flows. P1 is operated as a batch process and P2 is continuously working. These operational behaviours inflict the pattern of generated LPs. The respective singular LPs of both processes are then summed up to represent the overall LP of the depicted production route. The literature data categorized in Table 3 is used for the calculation of the accumulated IWH profiles. As previously mentioned, the time resolved pattern of the generated IWH is interlinked with the time resolved energy demand. Thus, the processes' behaviour – originating from the paradigm of discrete event simulation – can be adapted accordingly. The cumulative IWH profile is then again, the sum of all singular, process specific IWH profiles. We note that, within this example, thermal inertia effects are already included on average in the IWH profile of P1 energy-wise. Due to lack of underlying data their time resolved impact on the generated IWH profile cannot be depicted yet. Additionally, we like to outline that thermal inertia effects do not impact the generated IWH profiles on a holistic energy system level to that extent, which we aim for in this study (see section 2.1). Therefore, we like to outline again that the generation of IWH profiles via our methodology does not model individual processes explicitly but depicts their average energy consumption and generation time resolved and this may limit the application of our methodology.

2.3.2. Plant internal IWH recovery via heat exchangers

We showed in the previous section that waste heat potentials of all involved processes of a specific production route can be defined via the quantitative, time resolved parameters of the temperature difference and energy flow rate [25].

Following the definition of selected production routes and its maximum technical IWH potentials (Step 1 in Fig. 5), we investigate its technical recovery within heat exchangers next. In case of cumulating more than one IWH flow from different processes, resulting parameters from Table 3 are to be generated: The corresponding quantitative parameters for cumulative, mixed IWH flows from i out of m processes are calculated via formulas (3), for sensible heat transfer (4) and latent heat transfer (5):

$$\dot{Q}_{IWH,m} = \sum_{i=0}^m \dot{Q}_{IWH,i} \quad (3)$$

$$T_{IWH,m} = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^m \left(\left(\frac{1}{k_{IWH,i}} \right) \times T_{outlet,i} \right)}{\sum_{i=0}^m \left(\frac{1}{k_{IWH,i}} \right)} \quad \text{with } k_{IWH,i} = \frac{1}{\dot{m}_{Carrier,i} \times c_{p,Carrier,i}} \quad (4)$$

$$T_{IWH,m} = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^m (T_{outlet,i})}{m} \quad (5)$$

The corresponding HEX for recovering the technical IWH potentials time resolved is either set as operating in counter-current or co-current flow. Furthermore, a minimal temperature difference due to technical functionality and structural limits is defined within our methodology. We disregarded the options to specify HEX efficiency losses and cross-

Fig. 6. Order of simplified IWH profile calculation. Thermal inertia effects, as indicated, are averaged in the following summation of IWH profiles. The timely resolution of thermal inertia effects is neglected.

current flow.

Furthermore, we note that the generation of IWH profiles through our methodology does not include optimization analyses for the most efficient waste heat utilization. Therefore, we disregarded pinch point analyses and the construction of composite curves hence these calculations require time resolved optimization. Along this, we also like to note, that the possibility of including thermal energy storage is not part of the methodology yet. As energy storage is not specifically bound to the timely production behaviour of the production route (unlike currently involved production processes), a besides developed methodology for solely depicting time resolved charging and discharging profiles should be developed in the future. To incorporate this in the presented methodology, firstly, a classification of currently developed thermal storage solutions is to be made, secondly, a method for generating IWH profiles of energy storages on the basis of discrete event simulation is to be developed and thirdly, this method is to be incorporated in the existing solutions along different use case scenarios (e.g. application of thermal peak shifting, etc.).

Fig. 7 shows the allocation of IWH from process P2 to P1 within a counter-current operated HEX for either sensible (a) or latent heat transfer for e.g., steam supply (b). The externally supplied energy demand $\dot{Q}_{in,P1}$ of P1 is to be reduced by the recovery process. \dot{Q}_{IWH} is the overall waste heat potential of P2, \dot{Q}_{HEX} is defined as the maximum heat flow to be recovered and utilized in P1. To successfully transfer heat, the operational state of P1 requires a temperature difference, which is given through the difference of intake (cold-end) $T_{intake,P1}$ and operating temperature (hot-end) $T_{op,P1}$. This is well-defined by the second law of thermodynamics as heat only flows from a hot to a cold state as the entropy of an isolated system always increases [26]. A corresponding \dot{Q}/T diagram (Fig. 7) enables the graphical evaluation of heat transfer from P2 to P1 within the HEX. Within the \dot{Q}/T diagram, the top line (hot curve) indicates the heat discharged from P2, and the bottom line (cold curve) the required heating demand. The marked area shows the

transferred heat from P1 to P2 in total. Within this example, the mean conservative energy demand $\dot{Q}_{in,P1}$ can be substituted through the IWH recovery as the entire heating demand line in the \dot{Q}/T diagram can be covered by the hot curve without violating the minimal temperature difference T_{pp} (pinch point), which is given through the technical feasibility of heat conduction. Furthermore, the remaining heat flow $\dot{Q}_{excessIWH}$ of the hot curve (grey line) is to be discharged outside the manufacturing level at a temperature of T_{HEX} .

Fig. 8 shows an example of special cases of IWH \dot{Q}/T diagrams which can be depicted throughout our developed methodology. For all special cases, the minimal temperature difference is set to T_{pp} . We note that these examples outline analyses from a general, geometrical point of view for intersecting cold and hot curves in the context of assessing T_{HEX} or \dot{Q}_{HEX} . These analyses apply for sensible and latent heat transfer curves. For the latter, the slope of the curves is zero as shown in Fig. 3 (c) and (f).

Fig. 8 (a) resembles a counter-current flow HEX in which the operating temperature (hot-end) of the cold curve exceeds the outlet temperature (also hot-end) of the hot curve. In this case, only a fraction of the IWH can be internally recovered in P1. The remaining energy demand which lies between the temperatures $T_{op,P1}$ and $T_{outlet,P2}$ cannot be substituted entirely. Waste heat for external use remains.

Fig. 8 (b) shows a counter-current flow with a cold-end temperature of the hot curve above ambient temperature. Furthermore, the energy demand of the cold curve exhibits a smaller slope due to higher mass flows or a higher specific heat capacity compared to the hot-curve flow. Throughout this configuration, the generated IWH of P2 can be internally utilized for substituting a fraction of the energy demand of P1. No IWH for external use remains.

Fig. 8 (c) shows a counter-current flow- for latent heat transfer to the cold curve. Here, only a part of the required latent heat can be provided through the heat transfer.

Fig. 8 (d) resembles a co-current flow. Here, the cold curve intersects

Fig. 7. Waste heat recovery between processes P1 and P2 via counter-current flow for (a) sensible or (b) latent heat transfer.

Fig. 8. IWH recovery special cases: (a) Counter-current flow with a hot-end temperature of the cold curve above the hot-end temperature of the hot curve (sensible heat transfer), (b) Counter-current flow with a smaller slope and smaller cold-end temperature of the cold curve (sensible heat transfer), (c) Counter-current flow with no slope and smaller temperature level of the cold curve (latent heat transfer), (d) Co-current flow with the intersection between hot and cold curve (sensible heat transfer), (e) Co-current flow with the hot-end temperature of the cold curve above the cold-end temperature of the hot curve (sensible heat transfer), (f) Co-current flow with the smaller temperature level of cold curve (latent heat transfer).

the hot curve. As a result, only a fraction of the generated IWH can be internally recovered. Furthermore, the substitution of the energy demand of P1 can only be executed partially. Waste heat for external use remains.

Fig. 8 (e) is a co-current operated HEX of which the desired operating temperature of P1 lies above the cold-end temperature of the IWH generating P2 and the ambient temperature. This case allows the internal recovery of the entire generated IWH. However, because of the temperature configuration of the cold curve, only a fraction of the total energy demand of P1 can be substituted. No IWH for external use remains.

Fig. 8 (f) shows a co-current flow for latent heat transfer to the cold curve. Here, only a part of the required latent heat can be provided through the heat transfer.

To allocate recovered IWH internally, all involved processes (serial or parallel) are to be connected logically as retrieved from literature review and from our prior publication [10]. Excess heat can only be transferred if the intake temperature of an individual process equates (minus T_{pp}) the operating temperature (the outlet temperature) of the corresponding preceding process. Fig. 9 shows this approach for a

simplified serial production route in general.

Within our developed methodology, buffer units to depict process route integrated storage and stock items are implemented. For example, in the Iron & Steel industry, hot coils are often placed in storage [27] before being further processed. In the meantime, these products cool down and emit heat. As this energy is recoverable under our described theoretical technical potential [28], the buffer units can be declared as IWH potentials. The data of this technical potential is again retrieved in the same manner as already mentioned in section 2.3.1. Because of the lack of underlying data from literature for this special case, we apply a theoretical calculation first. Here, the overall heat content of the buffered items (e.g., 1 tonne of steel coils) is calculated through the temperature of the items (above ambient), the specific heat capacity of steel and mass (or mass flow) of the coils. An estimated loss term adjusts this theoretical potential to represent the technical potential. This energy is then emitted through thermal convection as the waste heat carrier of exhaust/cooling air. Furthermore, all buffer units operate at ambient temperature by default. Thus, these units can be placed within the production route to disrupt the temperature gradient if necessary.

Fig. 9. Temperature gradient of an exemplary production chain.

2.3.3. Calculation of excess IWH leaving the plant

The calculation of IWH which is currently not utilized internally within the plant can be specified as excess IWH potentials. These potentials can be either used by an enhanced plant's own IWH utilization or discharged from the plant for external use. The latter indicates the possibility for district heating application if the required conditions like timely behaviour, temperature range, etc. [4] are met.

The calculation of excess IWH potentials ($\dot{Q}_{\text{excessIWH}}$) depends on the definition of implemented system boundaries, as we introduced in section 2.2. Fig. 10 (a) and (b) depict the developed approach for calculating time resolved profiles through the application of different system boundaries. This simplified example contains a counter-current flow HEX configuration with intersecting hot and cold curves within the respective \dot{Q}/T diagram (sensible heat transfer). The minimal temperature difference T_{PP} is set accordingly. The intersection of energy flows with the specific system boundary defines the time resolved profile to be calculated. In this case, Fig. 10 (a) shows the result LP, when the system boundary is set to cover the energy demand $\dot{Q}_{\text{in,P1}}$ of P1. By defining the specific configuration of the implemented HEX, the fraction of the energy demand of P1 is substituted by \dot{Q}_{HEX} resulting in an adapted LP with reduced demands (see Fig. 10 (a)).

To calculate the respective excess IWH $\dot{Q}_{\text{excessIWH}}$, the system boundary is to be implemented as shown in Fig. 10 (b). As the boundary intersects both \dot{Q}_{IWH} and \dot{Q}_{HEX} , their mathematical difference resembles $\dot{Q}_{\text{excessIWH}}$ resulting in a – based upon the continuous behaviour of P2 – static profile.

With more than one HEXs implemented in a production route, the corresponding excess IWH profile is calculated by the sum of all $\dot{Q}_{\text{excessIWH}}$ profiles.

2.4. Methodology for IWH profile calculation for non-energy-intensive subsectors

The increased process and product variety in non-energy-intensive subsectors hinders bottom-up energy system analyses as applied in energy-intensive industries [10]. In our preceding study [10] we developed a new top-down approach to generate synthetic LPs (electricity and direct fuel) for non-energy-intensive subsectors. We now combine IWH calculations with the beforehand generated LPs to generate IWH profiles. Due to the nature of top-down calculations, all LPs and IWH profiles are simulated again in reference to the plant-level system boundary, as also described by our research aim (see Fig. 4).

Here, we apply waste heat fractions (WHF) to generate IWH profiles in combination with the existing synthetic LPs. The WHF f_{IWH} [-] is defined by formula (6):

$$f_{\text{IWH}} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{\text{excessIWH}}}{\dot{Q}_{\text{in}}} \quad (6)$$

As $\dot{Q}_{\text{excessIWH}}$ [W] is the rejected heat left unused within the plant border and \dot{Q}_{in} [W] the cumulative energy flow into the plant, which is responsible for generating IWH which is assumed to be e.g., natural gas.

2.4.1. Data collection

We conducted extensive literature research to identify WHFs for all industrial subsectors. We found that, because of their higher potential of IWH, a significant share of WHFs refers to energy-intensive subsectors. Although we apply the WHFs to determine the IWH profiles for non-energy-intensive subsectors mainly, we included the WHFs of energy-intensive industries in our investigation to complement and validate the WHFs of non-energy-intensive subsectors at the same time.

All included studies address excess IWH potentials, which are under current circumstances not recovered on site and therefore correspond to our definition of WHFs (see formula (6)). The studies vary regarding

Fig. 10. Application of system boundaries for a simplified production route, (a) expressing the results for energy demand after IWH recovery and (b) remaining excess IWH potentials.

their implemented data sources (e.g., via measurements at real-life industrial plants, via combustion equations from data from the EU Emission Trading System (ETS), via conducting cross-sectoral surveys, etc.), systemic applications (e.g., country, industrial subsector, etc.) and calculation approaches (e.g. reference temperature, etc.). In overall, the reference or minimum use temperature of the excess IWH is defined as the lower limit as part of the temperature difference, which accounts for the recoverable excess heat flow. We apply this information to examine cross-sectoral IWH potentials.

Helgerud et al. [29] conducted a study for assessing the IWH potentials of Norwegian industries. Within this study, the authors examine 72 physical manufacturing plants, which make up 63 % of the overall energy demand of the industrial sector in Norway. The plant's IWH potentials, which are not further used internally, are investigated and classified by temperature levels. The reference temperature of the respective IWH potentials is 0 °C.

McKenna et al. [5] published a study investigating IWH and their technical recovery potentials via a spatial model for the UK. One of the aims of the study is to quantify IWH and its utilization. The authors, therefore, gathered WHFs from literature themselves. These sources are not included in our research. The corresponding reference temperature of all WHFs is set to 0 °C.

Hammer et al. [30] assessed the IWH potentials of industrial plants by applying bottom-up calculations for energy-intensive industries and top-down approaches for non-energy-intensive subsectors. For the first approach, the process configuration and respective waste heat properties of real-life manufacturing plants are examined. Subsequent calculations yield the estimation of WHFs. We utilized some of the process specific waste heat data within our methodology for energy-intensive subsectors, see section 2.3. Regarding non-energy-intensive subsectors, the heat demand of all industrial subsectors can be identified based on the ETS reports. The authors then apply combustion equations for known energy carriers of these subsectors to calculate the expected IWH potentials. The reference temperature for these calculations is set to 0 °C.

Pellegrino et al. [31] conducted a study on the overall industrial sector in the US. The centrepiece of their study is the evaluation of energy usage and loss patterns of single industrial sites from different industrial subsectors. Energy-related industry surveys form the basis for the calculations. The collected energy losses, which are not further utilized within the plant, are classified as excess heat leaving the plant and referenced to the ambient temperature of 25 °C.

Papapetrou et al. [32] based their work on a study, which originally assessed WHFs for the UK in 2003 [33]. The authors further adjusted these fractions to apply to the European industry of 2015. They did this by incorporating the evolution of energy efficiency, technological advancements and conditions of the European industry in these twelve years. All waste heat calculations are referred to the ambient temperature of 25 °C.

Persson et al. [3] assessed the IWH availabilities in Europe on plant level and allocated these potentials to regional and national heat consumptions of the building sector to investigate the required capacities of a future European heating grid. The basic WHFs needed for these examinations originate from 410 European real-life manufacturing plants, grouped and averaged by their industrial subsector classification and are referred to the ambient temperature of 25 °C.

Brueckner et al. [6] investigated the IWH potentials of the entire industrial sector in Germany. The calculations are based on emission data surveys of all states in Germany. The waste heat potentials are then calculated via combustion equations and are checked for plausibility by conducting selected surveys and measurements on-site. Only waste heat within flue gas is considered within this study and the reference temperature is set to 35 °C. The author reasons the definition of this reference temperature due to the limited economic feasibility of IWH recovery and its overall low potential below 35 °C.

Pehnt et al. [34] calculated the remaining waste heat potentials of

the German industry for temperatures above 140 °C. To meet their goal, the authors also incorporated the WHFs from Helgerud et al. [29] for the subsectors of Iron & Steel, Chemical and Non-Metallic Minerals, but expanded the calculation of WHFs on other subsectors via top-down calculations of national energy balances.

To complement this literature survey, we included our own WHF calculations. We utilized the database *Industrial Sites: Industrial Database for EU28 + Norway* by Manz et al. [35] stating the referred subsector (NACE classification), the energy consumption and the IWH of >1000 single industrial sites in Europe. The data originates from different sources like the ETS, the European Pollutant Release and Transfer Register (E-PRTR), etc. as the retrieved information on site-specific emissions is used to adjust the mentioned parameters above. Only IWH above 100 °C is included in this database. We found 160 data points for the subsector Iron & Steel (NACE C24.1), 295 for Cement (NACE C23.5), 195 for Glass (NACE C23.1) and 410 for Pulp & Paper production (NACE C17) to be suitable for our calculations. By applying formula (6) we calculated the respective WHFs for these subsectors.

All surveyed WHFs are shown in Table 6 in the Appendix section.

2.4.2. Data analysis and calculation of maximum use temperature

We calculate the IWH profiles for non-energy-intensive industries by multiplying the corresponding WHFs (according to Table 6) with the LPs of the depicted manufacturing plant, generated according to the methodology described in [10]. To also successfully examine the exergetic potential (as described in section 2.1), the temperature level of the generated IWH flow is to be determined as well. The goal of our further investigations regarding the surveyed WHFs, depicted in Table 6, is therefore to compute IWH profiles together with the subsectors' averaged maximum excess temperature (hot-end) of the rejected IWH together with the defined reference / minimum use temperature (cold-end), which originates from stated literature sources from section 2.4.1.

The maximum excess temperature of IWH (T_{\max}) rejected from the industrial plant is generally not given in literature. Therefore, we apply further theoretical calculations including the given WHFs and reference / minimum use temperatures (T_{\min}) from the investigated literature studies to compute T_{\max} for every NACE subsector. We again conduct these evaluations within a respective \dot{Q}/T diagram, see Fig. 11, as T_{\max} can be determined from linear regression of the literature studies' T_{\min} values and corresponding assumptions of utilized thermal energy content within the plant.

In Fig. 11, the x-axis shows the relative rated thermal input based on the lower calorific value of the employed fuel. The y-axis shows the temperature in °C. For supplying useful energy to industrial end-use applications, the share of employed natural gas in comparison to all applied fuels in e.g. Austria accounts for around 54 % [36]. Here,

Fig. 11. Rated thermal input in contrast to adiabatic flame temperature and location of respective WHFs.

biogenic gases are excluded, but approximately make up for the same heat content as natural gas. Subsequently, we assume that natural gas, as the main employed fuel in industrial use, is to be incinerated at a stoichiometric air-to-fuel ratio of 1, whereas the condensation of involved water is disregarded (no involvement of latent heat transfers). Under these considerations, the respective adiabatic flame temperature is 1950 °C for natural gas [37]. This maximum value would be achieved within a theoretical system of no losses [38] or no heat transferred to other systems. Through this assumption, an additional datapoint next to the mentioned temperature values above (T_{\max} and literature values of T_{\min}) is included, additionally reinforcing the linear function in the \dot{Q}/T diagram. As Fig. 11 indicates, the total rated thermal input can be divided into the following three compartments:

- 1) The fraction of site-own internal heat use between temperatures of $T_{\text{adiabatic}}$ and T_{\max} in Fig. 11
- 2) The fraction of heat rejected but technical recoverable (WHF) between temperatures of T_{\max} and T_{\min} in Fig. 11
- 3) The fraction of heat “lost” or no longer considered as a result of the definition of reference / minimum use temperature T_{\min}

As mentioned above, for each NACE subsector listed in Table 6, the corresponding WHFs from literature are referred to different reference / minimum use temperatures T_{\min} : 0 °C, 25 °C, 35 °C, 100 °C, 140 °C, if available. The WHF externally utilized (e.g., in district heating) is a function of the reference temperature T_{\min} as e.g., higher T_{\min} equates to smaller shares of heat flows for properties of natural gas, while T_{\max} is fixed by the cumulative IWH generation of industrial processes. In this case, T_{\min} can also be referred to as the supply temperature of the given district heating system.

By incorporating the data point T_{\min} and the corresponding WHF into the linear \dot{Q}/T function/plot shown in Fig. 11, we can calculate the respective T_{\max} . Hence our literature survey states different T_{\min} values with varying WHFs based on individual methods, we averaged the resulting T_{\max} . Fig. 12 shows the exemplary case of this calculation for the subsector “NACE C10 – Manufacture of food products”: The literature survey (see Table 6) states WHFs for the three reference temperatures 0 °C, 25 °C and 35 °C. These data points are incorporated in the linear function disclosed by the rated thermal input [%] and $T_{\text{adiabatic}}$ of 1950 °C for natural gas, as described above. All three data points yield individual T_{\max} values, of which we calculated the average to be 215 °C. As the WHFs of literature sources originate from different methodologies and databases, an underlying deviation within the calculation of T_{\max} cannot be excluded definitively.

Naturally, more data regarding the WHFs of a corresponding subsector causes a more robust calculation of T_{\max} . Thus, our top-down approach finds in limitations in the depiction of T_{\max} for data sets with only one or two data points (e.g., “NACE C13 – Manufacture of textiles”). Additionally, there are also difficulties when examining IWH parameters of whole subsectors which are extremely heterogeneous in

Fig. 12. Exemplary \dot{Q}/T diagram and included WHFs of 0 °C, 25 °C and 35 °C of the subsector “NACE C10 – Manufacture of food products”.

terms of the product and process variety. We, therefore, made plausibility checks for these calculated T_{\max} values. For example, the calculation of T_{\max} of “NACE C13 – Manufacture of textiles” based upon just one value, results in a staggering 600.5 °C. Panayiotou et al. [20] state that, even though the subsector employs mainly low to medium-temperature processes, manufacturing plants also might deploy dirt removal and oxidation units, which operate at high temperature ranges up to 1200 °C. This underlines that our calculations of T_{\max} are subsector averaged examinations, heavily depending on the quality of the literature-based WHF.

3. Validation of developed bottom-up methodology

3.1. Overview

The functionality of the developed methodology is incorporated in a case study describing a simplified energy system of a real-life cement production plant in Austria, which directly corresponds to the explained methodology for energy-intensive industries of section 2.3. The goal of this case study is to depict the production route of the physical plant as accurately as possible via a bottom-up approach and generate synthetic LPs for electricity and fuel demands and internal and external IWH profiles of the site. Here, the focus especially lies on the generation of IWH profiles of cumulative IWH potentials, which leave the facility at plant level as excess IWH potentials. This practically employs the developed default scheme for industrial system boundaries from Fig. 4. All generated profiles are then compared to yearly energy demands and technical IWH potentials for validation since measured IWH profiles are not accessible. The yearly energy demands and technical IWH potentials of the site are a result of prior investigations conducted by Hammer et al. [30], which are not publicly available, but are to be described in the following section.

Fig. 13 depicts the overall process of IWH profile generation for this case study in line with our methodology described above. As declared, steps 1 and 2 are partly conducted by Hammer et al. [30] combined with additional data from literature and will be described in the following section. Step 3 contains the set-up of the to-be-depicted production line according to the logic of Fig. 5 from section 2.3.

Through publicly available company sources, the overall clinker production of the cement mill can be estimated at 78 t/h at full operation hours of 8000 h per year [30]. The reference temperature is set to 25 °C.

3.2. Calculation of yearly technical IWH potentials

Prior investigations on the real-life cement mill included the calculations of its yearly IWH potentials. These potentials are investigated as excess heat potentials, which could be further tapped from a technical point of view but are currently disregarded and rejected from the plant level. Regarding investigating these potentials, Hammer et al. [30] applied corresponding calculations to production units with the highest IWH potential as of cyclone preheater, rotary kiln and clinker cooler, shown in Fig. 14.

To accumulate a better understanding of heat flows within this usually closed system, we inserted sectional boundaries for those units into the overall production route, providing the opportunity to examine all processes as differentiated production steps.

Initial raw material mills grind the input materials (limestone, clay, ...) to meet the required particle size. Within these mills, the raw input material is preheated from waste heat $\dot{Q}_{\text{IWH,Cyc}}$ originating from the cyclone preheater. Here, the raw material is further heated until reaching the desired material temperature of around 900 °C [39]. The following calcinatory endothermically decomposes the limestone (CaCO_3) into carbon dioxide (CO_2) and lime (CaO) as basis material for cement clinker production at this temperature level [40]. The energy

Fig. 13. Process of conducting the selected case study.

Fig. 14. Production units included in IWH potential calculations (Energy demands e.g., based on main and auxiliary firing not depicted).

demand of the calciner is covered by waste heat from downstream cooling units $\dot{Q}_{IWH,Cool,a}$, hot flue gas $\dot{Q}_{IWH,Kiln,a}$ at around 1050 °C from the rotary kiln and auxiliary firing of fuels (e.g. alternative fuels) [41]. The rotary kiln sinters the incoming material to compact clinker granules at elevated temperatures of 1500–2000 °C [42]. The main burners inflicting the required heating demand are located at the far end of the rotary kiln. Thus, not only hot flue gas is generated ($\dot{Q}_{IWH,Kiln,a}$) but also thermal radiation heat of the kiln itself ($\dot{Q}_{IWH,Kiln,b}$). The hot clinker leaves the kiln at 1450 °C and is cooled to temperatures of around 120 °C in a subsequent clinker cooler [43]. This cooling process is carried out by the utilization of intake cooling air. 70 % of the hot cooling air leaving the clinker cooler is recovered for covering the heating demand in the calciner ($\dot{Q}_{IWH,Cool,a}$) while the residue ($\dot{Q}_{IWH,Cool,b}$) is discharged to an electrostatic precipitator [44].

As we already mentioned, Hammer et al. examined the technical IWH potentials of this plant statically. We utilize their process and mass specific IWH content values for our IWH profile generation. As this production line generally applies IWH in counter-current flow HEXs, we flowingly describe the calculations by Hammer et al. backward, starting at the process of clinker cooling:

Based on the temperature difference of the cooled-down clinker (1450 °C to 120 °C) and its mass flow of 78 t/h, the overall cooling demand ($\dot{Q}_{IWH,Cool,a} + \dot{Q}_{IWH,Cool,b}$) is calculated as 8.56 MW or 109.56 kWh/t by Hammer et al. The respective cooling air/residue flue gas leaves the clinker cooler at 275–300 °C [45]. As mentioned above and by Hammer et al., 70 % of this hot gas together with the flue gas from the rotary kiln $\dot{Q}_{IWH,Kiln,a}$ preheats the calciner. $\dot{Q}_{IWH,Kiln,a}$ is calculated based on combustion equations for firing alternative fuels. $\dot{Q}_{IWH,Kiln,b}$

describes the thermal radiation of the kiln. Through correspondence with personnel from the cement plant, Hammer et al. estimated the heat content of the thermal radiation at around 29.25 kWh/t at 300 °C. The cyclone preheater and the calciner are considered as one process to calculate the generated heat flow $\dot{Q}_{IWH,Cyc}$, which consists of three fractions stated by Hammer et al.:

- 1) The heat content of the hot CO₂ share within the flue gas mass flow, resulting from the decomposition of limestone
- 2) Hot flue gas share, resulting from firing direct fuels as auxiliary burners within the calciner
- 3) The heat content of 70 % recovered cooling air from the clinker cooler

The sum of the heat content of all three fractions is around 134.01 kWh/t. The thermal radiation of both units is disregarded due to their small energy content. The temperature of this mixed gaseous flow is calculated by applying formula (6) again and can be estimated at 300 °C, which is confirmed by literature (250–300 °C) [46].

3.3. Model description and simulation

Based on the calculations by Hammer et al. above, the IWH profiles of the production route are simulated, which is to be described followingly. The full production route of this case is shown in Fig. 15.

Due the complexity of the examined production route and its underlying energy system, certain assumptions and simplifications had to be made: The residual heat content of the cooled-down clinker at 120 °C is generally removed in a follow-up post-cooling process step. This

Fig. 15. Design of the selected production route for simulation. Left: Production route with associated IWH flows, allocated HEXs and system boundaries, Right: Temperature chart as of intake and operating temperature of each process.

reduces the thermal stress of the material before further processing in clinker/cement mills [47]. We investigated 14.19 kWh/t to be cooled off within the post-cooling units but disregarded the implementation of this unit hence its general low energy consumption within the overall energy system. Alternatively, we attributed the IWH content to the follow-up cement mills as $\dot{Q}_{IWH,CM}$. Through personal correspondence, we found out that two cement mills are deployed at the real-life production facility. We, thus, divided the production flow of 78 t/h equally to both parallel processes, see Fig. 15.

The clinker cooler, rotary kiln and calcinatory are operated continuously. We placed the HEX 2 (Fig. 15) in counter flow operation recovering $\dot{Q}_{IWH,Cool,a}$ and $\dot{Q}_{IWH,Kiln,a}$.

Hammer et al. [30] did not further investigate the exhaust air leaving the cyclone preheater because of its general low IWH potential. In the real-life plant and within literature reviews, the exhaust air from the cyclone preheater is led into the raw material mills to early initiate the water removal process and to also precipitate gaseous SO_2 in the exhaust air [48]. We, therefore, included this IWH recovery within HEX 1 (Fig. 15), which reduces the excess technical IWH potential.

Overall, the IWH flows $\dot{Q}_{IWH,RMM}$, $\dot{Q}_{IWH,Kiln,b}$, $\dot{Q}_{IWH,Cool,b}$ and $\dot{Q}_{IWH,CM}$ contribute to the total amount of technical excess IWH potentials, which will be time resolved within the simulation. The heat flows crossing the process specific system boundaries in Fig. 15 are calculated accordingly. The corresponding operating temperatures of each process are taken

from literature research [48]. The overall temperature chart of this production route is also depicted in Fig. 15. We note, that – as declared in section 2.3.2 – the intake temperatures for process specific allocation of waste heat flows originate from the operating temperatures of the preceding processes.

All incorporated IWH flows are summarised in Table 4. For example, $\dot{Q}_{IWH,RMM}$ is neither known from literature nor calculated by Hammer et al. [30]. Therefore, this energy flow is not stated but can be investigated within our simulation: $\dot{Q}_{IWH,RMM}$ is to be constituted by determining certain degrees of freedom:

Table 4

Implemented IWH flows including their respective waste heat energy carrier, upper temperature limit (hot-end) and prior calculated energy content.

IWH Flow	Waste Heat Energy Carrier	Upper Temperature (Hot-End) [$^{\circ}C$]	Energy Content [kWh/t _{clinker}]
$\dot{Q}_{IWH,RMM}$	Exhaust Air	>58 $^{\circ}C$	To be calculated
$\dot{Q}_{IWH,Cyc}$	Exhaust Air	250–300 $^{\circ}C$	134.01 kWh/t
$\dot{Q}_{IWH,Kiln,a}$	Flue Gas	1050 $^{\circ}C$	210.50 kWh/t
$\dot{Q}_{IWH,Kiln,b}$	Exhaust Air	251 $^{\circ}C$	29.25 kWh/t
$\dot{Q}_{IWH,Cool,a}$	Flue Gas	275–300 $^{\circ}C$	76.70 kWh/t
$\dot{Q}_{IWH,Cool,b}$	Exhaust Air	275–300 $^{\circ}C$	32.86 kWh/t
$\dot{Q}_{IWH,CM}$	Exhaust Air	120 $^{\circ}C$	14.19 kWh/t

Table 5

Finale comparison of IWH potentials and energy consumption, including the results from this case study and the calculations of Hammer et al.

	Our Calculations [GWh]	Hammer et al. [30] [GWh]	Deviation [%]
IWH potential 25–50 °C	17.13 GWh	18.37 GWh	7 %
IWH potential 50–100 °C	34.27 GWh	35.77 GWh	4 %
IWH potential 100–400 °C	98.75 GWh	106.80 GWh	7 %
Sum IWH potential	150.15 GWh	160.94 GWh	7 %
Electricity consumption	66.67 GWh	78.13 GWh	15 %
Direct fuel consumption	624.30 GWh	610.76 GWh	2 %
Sum energy consumption	690.97 GWh	688.89 GWh	1 %
Share of IWH potential to energy consumption	21.7 %	23.3 %	7 %

- 1) $\dot{Q}_{IWH,RMM}$ is a fraction of the recovered $\dot{Q}_{IWH,Cyc}$.
- 2) The overall specific thermal capacity of raw material $c_{p,RawMaterial}$ for a temperature range of 25–58 °C is given.
- 3) The upper temperature limit of the exhaust air shall exceed 58 °C as the raw material is fully heated throughout this IWH recovery.

The minimum temperature difference T_{pp} at both HEXs is set to a minimum of 10 °C. All further process specific properties are based upon our prior examinations regarding load profile generation [10].

3.4. Case study results and discussion

By designing all dedicated IWH flows in Table 4, HEX 1 (between cyclone/calcinatory and raw material mill) and HEX 2 (between clinker cooler, rotary kiln and cyclone/calcinatory) can be defined accordingly. Based on the three points of configuration the transferred heat flow in HEX 1 can be depicted by a corresponding \dot{Q}/T diagram, shown in Fig. 16: $\dot{Q}_{IWH,Cyc}$ represents the overall heat flow of the hot curve, the heating demand of the raw material mill the cold curve. The marked area is the overall energy recovered through HEX 1. As it can be observed in Fig. 16, the entire heating demand of the raw material mill can be covered by recovery of $\dot{Q}_{IWH,Cyc}$.

The marked square indicates the outlet temperature of HEX 1 $T_{HEX 1}$. The share of the hot curve which is not recovered in HEX 1 equals the unused IWH potential, which we associate to $\dot{Q}_{IWH,RMM}$ in this case. Therefore, the average heat flow of $\dot{Q}_{IWH,RMM}$ can be estimated at around 105 kWh/t at 221 °C.

HEX 2 is defined in an according manner, however, is not explicitly explained in this study.

All not recovered heat flows like the internally unused potential of the plant shown in Fig. 16 are calculated time resolved, based upon the paradigm of discrete event simulation as described in section 2.3.

Fig. 17 shows the results of the IWH calculations of this case study for a time frame of 24 h. The black curve indicates the overall IWH profile as a sum of the dedicated exergetic levels according to Table 1, which we obtained through the calculations.

There is no IWH share of the higher exergetic level >400 °C, which can also easily be derived from the information of upper temperatures of heat flows crossing the system boundary of the depicted production route, which are all set at <400 °C (see Table 4). The main share of the IWH potential can be found at the high-grade exergy level of 100–400 °C, which corresponds to the processes' upper temperatures in Table 4. In comparison, medium- and low-grade exergy IWH flows are lower affiliating to smaller temperature differences in these levels (25 °C and 50 °C) leading to smaller absolute heat flow values.

In regard to the time resolved pattern, it can be observed, that the overall IWH profile exhibits high fluctuations. As can be investigated in Fig. 15, three out of five processes generating unused IWH potentials are operated batch-wise. This operating condition includes standstill and loading times causing a timely fluctuating behaviour, which, thus, explains the dominance of the generated fluctuations.

The area under the profiles represents the accumulated energy-wise IWH potential within the time frame of 24 h. We calculate the area under the curves and scale the time frame further up to meet the full operation hours of 8000 h per year. This enables the comparison to the calculated static and technical IWH potentials by Hammer et al. [30]. As the data regarding specific IWH flows is based on their prior calculations, the deviation of our IWH profiles is expected to be minor. We furthermore generated electricity and direct fuel LPs throughout our prior developed methodology and compare the corresponding energy consumption to the static calculations by Hammer et al.

Table 5 shows the results of these evaluations. It can be observed that the overall deviation of yearly IWH potentials is – as expected – in an acceptable deviation range of 7 %, resulting from 150.15 GWh from our simulation and 160.94 GWh from Hammer et al. [30]. This deviation also corresponds well to the results within the three exergetic levels and is in general lower than the results from Hammer et al. [30]. This can be reasoned as we further implemented a HEX 1, which recovers IWH for the raw material mill, reducing the overall potential by 29 kWh/t or 18 GWh on average.

Fig. 16. Q/T diagram of HEX 1.

Fig. 17. Time resolved IWH profiles including exergetic classification of defined temperature levels.

As we utilized process specific data from literature further on top of the calculations by Hammer et al. these deviations could additionally be reasoned.

In regard to the generation of LPs for the calculation of electricity and direct fuel consumption, we employed our already existing methodology. This bottom-up methodology uses process specific energy consumption data from literature sources. Hammer et al. [30] utilize top-down approaches for calculating the energy consumption of the plant by investigating ETS databases. We like to note the small deviation between the two different calculation approaches. The maximum deviation of 15 % can be observed within electricity consumption.

In this study, the share of technical IWH potential compared to the calculated energy consumption equals 21.7 %. This means that within our case study, we investigated almost a quarter of the yearly energy demand of the plant to be left unused as recoverable IWH potential. There are still various possibilities for utilizing this fraction: For example, this potential can be employed further within the plant for preheating purposes (as we demonstrated within HEX 1). The excess heat could also be potentially stored in seasonal heat storages for residential buildings or employed as steam in site-specific power generation [49]. Because the IWH potentials are still generated at high-temperature levels, current studies and investigations propose a direct thermal linkage with other industrial plants in the vicinity of the IWH producer to reduce the energy consumption of the targeted plant [50]. Furthermore, applicable incorporation within district heating systems might be advisable as well as long as its limitations (e.g. flow temperature range) are not violated [14].

In conclusion, the investigated case study exhibits acceptable results in terms of deviation from the preceding examinations of Hammer et al. [30].

4. Conclusion

Industrial waste heat (IWH) forms a central point of contact for future decarbonization measures in industry. In the context of time resolved IWH, we found that current studies either investigate single technology and process implementation for recovering IWH on a highly detailed level minute-wise or spatial on subsector level on a monthly or yearly basis. We concluded that no solution has been developed yet, which enables the generation of time resolved IWH on plant level for the entire industrial sector. As this establishes our research aim, we have developed two methodological approaches for energy-intensive and non-energy-intensive industrial subsectors which cover this research gap: Energy-intensive subsectors are well documented in literature and deploy only a limited amount of different production processes and principles [10]. We therefore developed a bottom-up approach, which

connects individual processes to production routes and simulates the generated IWH based upon discrete event simulation. Non-energy-intensive subsectors deploy a vast range of different production processes and are thus to be investigated top-down. Here, we surveyed waste heat fractions from different literature sources and analysed them along thermodynamical calculations. The resulting fractions can then be employed with already generated load profiles to calculate time resolved IWH of individual industrial plants. For both approaches, we presented practical examples to constitute their functionality. In line with both methodological approaches, we now reflect on the hypotheses raised in section 1.2:

- H1: The implementation of system boundaries can be regarded as the basis of calculations for generating time resolved IWH profiles. Depending on the defined system boundaries, energy flow calculations vary regarding their results. This was practically proven by applying the standardized system boundaries of section 2.2 in the shown case study of section 3. The outlined example demonstrates the practical implementation of boundaries and their implications. As a result, it can be stated that system boundaries inflict the generated IWH profiles in terms of both time and temperature-resolved patterns.
- H2: In both proposed methodological approaches (for energy-intensive subsectors – see section 2.3 – for non-energy-intensive subsectors – see section 2.4) we found that the combination of energy flows and operating or waste heat temperatures is needed to correctly depict the timely resolution of generated IWH. This is in line with our theoretical definition of waste heat in section 2.1 and our practical investigations within the case study in section 3 proving this hypothesis.
- H3: While investigations in our shown \dot{Q}/T diagrams handle mathematically averaged loads, the simulated IWH flows of time resolved profiles within internal heat exchangers or outside the plant can be subject to significant fluctuations. This, however, poses a major challenge for holistic energy system analyses. Especially, batch operated production processes inflict unstable IWH generation patterns to the overall time resolved profiles. This means that time resolved IWH assessments are required for exploiting the full potential of IWH, especially for timely unstable production processes.

The investigation of time resolved IWH offers novel insights for exploiting the whole potential this measure might bear. As a first step, our study examines this field of research successfully uncovering the complexity of this topic. This compels us to point out the necessity of examining this field of research even further. As the optimization of production routes is not a topic of this current study, it might be an

important factor in future research. For example, alternative IWH recovery technologies like ORC, thermoelectric generators etc. (as explained in section 2.1) shall be incorporated in the methodology. Furthermore, e.g., pinch point analyses in also time resolved \dot{Q}/T diagrams within optimization frameworks could potentially unravel these problem areas and give opportunities to utilize IWH potentials further. Also, our investigations can feed into holistic system analyses by e.g., combining spatial resolutions with IWH profiles to develop national decarbonization scenarios. Furthermore, our future work can also benefit from more detailed technological analysis, also incorporating e.g., thermal inertia effects or thermal energy storage applications into the methodology if the required data is available to a sufficient extent. Regarding thermal energy storage, next research steps can be taken by analysing the literature on current storage solutions and incorporating them along selected use case/scenarios (e.g. thermal peak shaving) in the existing methodology on the basis of discrete event simulation. Concerning the methodology for non-energy-intensive subsectors, more data on waste heat fractions can impact the overall approach in a beneficial way. This also provides room for further investigations like incorporating other energy carriers or water condensation within flue gas into the presented fit function. Regarding this, our study can be

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Paul Josef Binderbauer: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Writing – original draft. **Andreas Hammer:** . **Elisabeth Lachner:** . **Nikolaus Klingenstein:** Conceptualization, Methodology. **Thomas Kienberger:** .

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix

Table 6

Summary of literature research regarding WHFs [-] of NACE classified industrial subsectors; Maximum Use Temperature from our calculations.

NACE-2	NACE-3	Description	Helgerud et al. [29]	McKenna et al. [5]	Hammer et al. [30]	Pellegrino et al. [31]	Papapetrou et al. [32]	Persson et al. [3]	Brueckner et al. [6]	Pehnt et al. [34]	Own IWH Calculations	Calculated Max. Use Temperature T_{max} [°C]
10		Manufacture of food products	0.15	0.1			0.05	0.1	0.1			215 °C
11		Manufacture of beverages	0.15	0.1			0.05	0.1	0.14			241 °C
12		Manufacture of tobacco products					0.05		0.12			195,75 °C
13		Manufacture of textiles							0.29			600,5 °C
14		Manufacture of wearing apparel							0.06			152 °C
15		Manufacture of leather and related products				0.27			0.2			488,25 °C
16		Manufacture of wood and of products of wood and cork							0.1			230 °C
17		Manufacture of pulp and paper products			0.18	0.2	0.19	0.25	0.09		0.09	319,5 °C
18		Printing and reproduction of recorded media					0.06		0.03			117,75 °C
19		Manufacture of coke and refined petroleum products				0.28						571 °C
	19.2	Manufacture of refined petroleum products				0.28		0.25				541,75 °C
20		Manufacture of chemicals and chemical products		0.1		0.1	0.04	0.25	0.09	0.08		245 °C
21		Manufacture of basic pharmaceutical products and pharmaceutical preparations							0.08	0.03		194,75 °C

(continued on next page)

Table 6 (continued)

NACE-2	NACE-3	Description	Helgerud et al. [29]	McKenna et al. [5]	Hammer et al. [30]	Pellegrino et al. [31]	Papapetrou et al. [32]	Persson et al. [3]	Brueckner et al. [6]	Pehnt et al. [34]	Own IWH Calculations	Calculated Max. Use Temperature T_{max} [°C]
22		Manufacture of rubber and plastic products							0.17	0.03		282,5 °C
23		Manufacture of other non-metallic mineral products	0.4	0.1		0.25	0.24	0.25	0.15			440,3 °C
	23.1	Manufacture of glass and glass products	0.4	0.2	0.57	0.25			0.15	0.03	0.19	471,45 °C
	23.2	Manufacture of refractory products	0.4		0.32	0.25			0.15			514 °C
	23.3	Manufacture of clay building materials	0.4		0.36	0.25			0.15			527 °C
	23.5	Manufacture of cement, lime and plaster	0.4	0.15	0.21	0.25			0.15		0.15	421,87 °C
24		Manufacture of basic metals	0.3						0.19			495,25 °C
	24.1	Manufacture of basic iron and steel and of ferro-alloys	0.3		0.19		0.33	0.25	0.19	0.3	0.33	563,75 °C
	24.2	Manufacture of tubes, pipes, hollow profiles and related fittings, of steel	0.3		0.18				0.19			436,75 °C
	24.4	Manufacture of basic precious and other non-ferrous metals	0.12	0.1			0.06	0.25	0.19	0.03		271 °C
25		Manufacture of fabricated metal products							0.19	0.03		302 °C
26		Manufacture of computer, electronic and optical products							0.18			386 °C
27		Manufacture of electrical equipment							0.31			639,5 °C
28		Manufacture of machinery and equipment							0.16	0.03		272,75 °C
29		Manufacture of motor vehicles, trailers and semi-trailers							0.12	0.03		233,75 °C
30		Manufacture of other transport equipment							0.38			776 °C
31		Manufacture of furniture							0.12			269 °C
32		Other manufacturing							0.08			191 °C
Reference / Minimum Use Temperature T_{min} from literature [°C]			0 °C	0 °C	0 °C	25 °C	25 °C	25 °C	35 °C	140 °C	100 °C	

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